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A Creative Folio

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The Melody of Numbers

There was a group of friends in Mathville who liked to make music. The first group always began the tune, raising the notes higher and higher, never looking back.

One day, a new acquaintance appeared- someone who could still the music and place a little calm between the notes. With this individual, the song might actually start from square one.

And then there were a few brave musicians who could play both the high notes of delight and the low notes of thought and make the melody rich and balanced.

Soon brilliant brains came who loved to break melodies into perfect little chunks sharing every beat and every pause so everybody may join in harmony.

Mysterious artists drifted in from afar with sounds that danced on forever, never repeating, never settling, always moving with a hint of magic.

At last, the wise old conductor gathered everyone together.

“Each of you has your own special sound,” smiled the conductor. “When all of you play together, you create a masterpiece that fills our world with wonder.”

And so, the friends of Mathville realized that each sound that was distinct made their song full and their music resonated through the land encouraging all that listened.